

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH SKILLS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *the article describes the main means of communication in the process of teaching the native language in creative schools, the system, methods and means of forming speech skills from speech skills, the type, classification and description of educational tasks. It gives an idea of the types of educational tasks that form impressive speaking skills in accordance with the norms of literary pronunciation among students of the creative schools.*

Keywords: *literary pronunciation, expressive speech, conversational speech, conversational skills, educational tasks, exercises, pronunciation exercises, classification of educational tasks, text, accents, logical accents.*

Since ancient times, speech has served as the main tool in the management of society. Every person conveys his opportunities, goals, and dreams through speech, but the result depends on the level of speech, execution - pronunciation, and the tone of the speech. In the world education system, special attention is paid to the student's oral presentation and speaking. Especially the methods used in the teaching of international languages are proving themselves in many cases. In particular, the approach to the development of specific speaking skills in teaching English as a second language is proving itself in today's experiments. At this point, the requirement for speaking skills is suitable to a certain extent for teaching Uzbek as a state language, but it is not suitable for mother tongue education.

In linguistic didactics, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of speaking and speaking. International language teaching includes listening comprehension, reading, and writing skills, as well as speaking, which is appropriate for a second language. A student can speak his mother tongue in the family before coming to school, but he cannot give a speech. Teaching public speaking to students in general secondary education system, especially in presidential and creative schools, which prepare the leaders of the country, is one of the urgent tasks.

At this point, it is necessary to comment on the concepts of speaking and speaking. Speaking is the free expression of a student's or a specific person's opinion in an oral form, in a common language.

Speaking is a purposeful speech with a specific system that requires special preparation by the speaker, follows the rules of literary language and literary pronunciation. Speech is not taught in our schools today. That is why the student cannot give a meaningful, logical and effective speech to the team in unfamiliar speech situations, meetings, celebrations, anijuman.

In order to speak fluently and effectively, the student must have the necessary vocabulary. As G.Hamroev noted, "It is necessary to increase the vocabulary by continuously memorizing various instructive texts".

In order for students to develop speaking skills, they must have the necessary vocabulary, and the training process must be properly organized. O.Usmonova cites dialects as the reason for difficulties in solving this problem. The researcher points out that the issue of pronunciation in Uzbek is not studied and this in this regard, he relies on the valuable opinions of scientist

F.K.Kamolov and professor S.I. Ibrohimov, who were the first to set standards of literary pronunciation.

In this regard, the following thoughts of H.Nematov are still relevant for mother tongue education: "It is impossible and necessary to teach a high school student all the linguistic knowledge accumulated by mankind over the centuries. Therefore, choosing the most necessary knowledge from the mother tongue is one of the main issues.

The main criterion for choosing knowledge from the mother tongue is its level of usefulness and practical application. We understand useful knowledge from the mother tongue as the knowledge that serves to form the skills of children's literate writing, creative thinking, correct and fluent expression of the product of thought in oral and written forms in accordance with the speech conditions, and ensures their upbringing and development in the spirit of high human qualities.

We observe that the issue of literary pronunciation and its standards has been thoroughly studied in the languages of the developed countries of the world [English, French, etc.]. In this regard, phonetic exercises are effectively used in the world experience, including in English

The speech of today's pupils, students, and even some older intellectuals, especially teachers, proves that the correct pronunciation of some sounds characteristic of the Uzbek language cannot be adequately taught with simple, traditional exercises.

According to G. Hamroev, one end of the problem goes back to the issue of mother tongue teaching in secondary general education schools. Literary pronunciation is a sign of culture. Speech sounds, which are considered the main unit of pronunciation in the secondary general education system from the 5th grade

Systematic teaching begins in the "Phonetics" department. According to the educational requirements of the "Phonetics" department, students are also required to learn the correct pronunciation and spelling rules along with speech sounds.

Pupils have specific requirements for the development of speaking skills, a mechanism for implementation. They can be classified and described as follows:

I. Development of literary pronunciation skills

1. Work on hard-to-pronounce vowels.
2. Work on hard-to-pronounce consonants.
3. Pronouncing the words in the text in syllables.
4. Working on word accents.
5. Practice reading in syllables.

II. Increase vocabulary

1. Work on proverbs and maxims.
2. Work on phrases.
3. Work on figurative expressions.
4. Work on synonyms.
5. Exercise of replacing figurative expressions with words.

III. Teaching to effectively use the opinion of others in one's speech

1. Exercise of choosing another sentence that gives the same meaning instead of the sentence
2. Exercise of using introductory words interchangeably
3. Exercise of using auxiliary words interchangeably
4. Exercise of verbal conversion of quotation sentences into appropriate sentences
5. Speaking exercise using simple sentences

IV. Teaching speech techniques

1. Exercise of reading the text in different tones
2. Exercise of narrating the text in a solemn tone
3. Exercise of resonating the content of the text with one sentence
4. The exercise of presenting the content of the text in the form of propaganda
5. Exercise of promoting the content of the text
6. Exercise of reciting the text by heart

These training processes develop students' first of all literary pronunciation skills, increase their vocabulary, prepare them for speaking, presentation and advocacy. The main educational task that forms the student's speaking skills in classes is an exercise. Tasks and questions serve to evaluate the achieved results, organize the process and form thinking skills.

The content of the tasks given for working on the text should be pragmatic in nature, otherwise it will not have any practical value and will weaken the attention of the student. Each future speaker should first of all work on pronunciation problems in his speech, practice tirelessly. Otherwise, any well-thought-out speech can lose its effectiveness and importance.

The conclusion is that in all educational institutions, the main part of training on the formation of speaking skills should consist of exercises. Also, exercise processes should be systematic, one complementing the other. The speech teaching technology offered by us can be used not only in presidential and creative schools, but also in training future teachers in higher education institutions.

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